

Te Kete Manaaki Taonga

Whatungarongaro te tangata toitū te whenua

As man disappears from sight, the land remains

Maori is Taonga

Today, The New Zealand Curriculum affirms the value of te Reo Māori as the indigenous language of New Zealand. Increasingly, New Zealanders understand that te Reo Māori and Tikanga Māori are essential components of this country's heritage. While they define Māori identity in particular, they are integral to the identity of all New Zealanders. Yet for all the positive indications of change, only 3 percent of New Zealanders can actually converse in te reo Māori. If this is to change, all schools will need to provide their students with the opportunities to learn te reo Māori that are available through The New Zealand Curriculum

Importance of understanding and learning Maori:

- participate with understanding and confidence in situations where te Reo and Tikanga Māori predominate and integrate language and cultural understandings into their lives;
- strengthen Aotearoa New Zealand's identity in the world;
- broaden their entrepreneurial and employment options to include work in an ever-increasing range of social, legal, educational, business, and professional settings.

Te Kete Manaaki Taonga

Te Reo Maori Curriculum Guidelines Book → Pg 8-11 for assignments

→ Te Reo is an ancestral language of Maori, it links to their identity, culture and ^{rich} complex language. That is why Te Reo Maori is Taonga because their identities, ^{large} communication, culture and ~~trad~~ values are represented through it. The language holds history, ancestors and their values.

→ The first language - Te Reo Maori was used and consists of lots of history, heritage, culture

→ Primary source of information in our country.

Benefits of Learning Te Reo (Pg 14)

- Cultural**
 - deepens understanding of Tikanga Maori, language, culture, place, heritage, shaping identity
- Social**
 - deepens understanding of human experiences, build better relationships
- Economic and Career**
 - more Maori jobs & career Govt jobs.
- Linguistic**
 - helps develop linguistic skills, develop attitudes, understanding that they can transfer to other languages
- Cognitive**
 - they learn more ways of learning, knowing, thinking, about their own capabilities.
- Personal**
 - Increased sense of Belonging - contribution as citizens of multicultural society

KORERO- TE REO MAORI

Maori Alphabet & Sounds

	H	K	M	N	P	R	T	W	NG	WH
A	Ha	Ka	Ma	Na	Pa	Ra	Ta	Wa	Nga	Wha
E	He	Ke	Me	Ne	Pe	Re	Te	We	Nge	Whe
I	Hi	Ki	Mi	Ni	Pi	Ri	Ti	Wi	Ngi	Whi
O	Ho	Ko	Mo	No	Po	Ro	To	Wo	Ngo	Who
U	Hu	Ku	Mu	Nu	Pu	Ru	Tu	Wu	Ngu	Whu

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why is Te Reo Maori considered 'taonga' (treasure)?

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Whakapapa

The knowledge held within whakapapa reveals the connections to Māori, providing a base for tikanga Māori, a philosophical system ensuring one's existence.

Whakapapa links us to our ancestors; to where we have come from; to our surroundings; to our tupuna; to ranginui me papa-tū-ā-nuku; to our whenua, our tūrangawaewae; to our hapū, iwi, moana, awa, waka, whānau [Mead, 2003, p. 43]. Whakapapa is the connection of spiritual beliefs to identity [Metge, 1995] cultural practice, and tribal structures [Durie, 2002; Broughton, 1993; Moeke-Pickering, 1996].

Maori language, culture, lineage, kinship, fishing, land, and agriculture is important and is taonga. It is passed down from generation to generation.

TAMARIKI: OUR TAONGA

Employing the principles from the Te Whāriki Curriculum (Ministry of Education, 1996) requires application of a holistic approach to the image of the Māori child.

Whakamana

“The Māori child has the right to be and feel empowered as a valued and unique individual, and as an integral member of whānau, hapū, iwi, and the society of Aotearoa overall” (pp. 7-10).

Kotahitanga

“The Māori child is a whole person and has the right to be treated in the wholeness of intellect, spirit, and being” (pp. 7-10).

Whanaungatanga

“The Māori child descends from a culture and history based on strong genealogical links and relationships, and has the right to be respected within the full context of those links and relationships” (pp. 7-10).

Ngā Hononga

“The Māori child exists within a society of extensive relationships, and has the right to know, contribute positively to and benefit from those relationships” (pp. 7-10).

The notion of tapu and mana of the Māori child explains that the child comes from the blood descendants of “godly origins, from human origins, from earthly origins, from a unique cultural heritage, traditions, and discourse, and from universal and ancient origins” (Early Childhood Development, 2002, p. 6).

Naku te rourou nau te
rourou ka ora ai te iwi

With your basket and my
basket the people will
live

2. Animal jungle: Using tamariki artwork,
animals, colours, numbers

3. Waitangi day activity: Biculturalism,
making Korowai with tamariki

Blooming buds projects and evidences-

1. Te whaariki based learning : Learning
stories, pictures and links

2. Animal jungle: Using tamariki artwork,
animals, colours, numbers

Anecdotes from daily Practices

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